

Current Concepts and Trends In Forensic Odontology - A Review

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Abstract

Forensic Odontology is a relatively new science that utilizes the dentist's knowledge to serve the judicial system. It has established itself as an important indispensable science in medicolegal matters and in particular in identification of the dead. Worldwide, dentists qualified in forensic science are giving expert opinion in cases related to human identification, bitemark analysis, craniofacial trauma and malpractice. Dental professionals have a major role to play in keeping accurate dental records and providing all necessary information so that legal authorities may recognize malpractice, negligence, fraud or abuse, and identify unknown humans. This article presents a literature review referring to the understanding the various methods along with their applications employed in forensic odontology.

Keywords: Forensic Odontology, Tongue prints, Dental Identification, Bite marks, Cheiloscopsy, Rugoscopy

Introduction

Forensic odontology has been defined by the Fédération Dentaire Internationale (FDI) as 'that branch of dentistry which, in the interest of justice, deals with the proper handling and examination of dental evidence, and with the proper evaluation and presentation of dental findings'. It primarily deals with identification, based on recognition of unique features present in an individual's dental structures. Forensic dentistry plays a major role in identification in man made or natural disasters events which result in multiple fatalities that may not be identifiable through conventional methods such as visual recognition or even fingerprints.^[1]

As dental surgeon has to actively involved in various objectives of forensic dentistry like age and sex determination, personal identification of unknown deceased person, analyzing bite marks as evidence, participating in mass disaster, studying lip prints, giving evidence in child abuse and in civil and criminal litigation, his role in personal identification and criminal investigation is very much important, as his evidence would be very much useful in law and justice.

Dentist's role in criminal investigation

includes collection of information from bite marks, lip prints and teeth found in the crime sites like, quarrel, robbery, murder and rape.^[2]

Methods used for Identification^[3]

1. Visual Information
2. Personal or medical information:
 - a. General information: Height, weight, build, age, presence or absence of hair, its colour and style, eye colour, facial hair, facial characteristics
 - b. Specific information: Scars, tattoos, birth-marks, operations, amputations, breast implants, old injuries, medical conditions, body piercings
 - c. Radiological information: Anatomical abnormalities, foreign bodies (prosthesis)
3. Clothing: Items last seen wearing, patterns of fabrics, labels, alterations/repairs
4. Personal effects and documentation: Contents of pockets and bags, jewellery may be recognizable or have specific inscriptions/engravings.
5. Dentistry

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6. Fingerprints: May be on record, but it is often necessary to take them from personal items in the home or workplace for comparison purposes
7. Feet: Foot prints are kept on record by some armed forces. Records from a chiropodist/podiatrist may hold useful information
8. DNA profiling

Dental Record and Identification

Dental identification assumes a primary role in the identification of remains when postmortem changes, traumatic tissue injury or lack of a fingerprint record invalidate the use of visual or fingerprint methods.^[4]

Collection of dental postmortem examination information^[3]

The following will be noted:

1. Dental arch shape, alignment, occlusion
2. Number and position of teeth present and missing
3. Size, shape, position and material of any restorations, presence and position of decayed surfaces
4. Denture and other appliance design and material
5. Individual tooth characteristics, for example tooth wear, fractures, anomalies of size, shape and colour
6. Hard tissue and soft tissue (if present) status, abnormalities or pathologies
7. Any other findings of interest, or clues to age, race, diet, occupation etc.

Figure 1: Tools In Forensic Odontology

Bite Mark Analysis

In forensic sciences, odontology evidence is the third most accurate technique of fingerprint and DNA analysis identification.^[5] According to a study by Pretty and Turnbull, the bite mark analysis is based on the factor that human dentition is unique and its uniqueness is rendered during biting that aids in the identification.^[6] Bite marks can deform because of the flexibility and elasticity of the skin. The amount of pressure exerted while biting, along with the body posture and the angle of the maxilla

and mandible during the bite, can all determine the appearance of a bite mark.^[7]

Literature reveals different methods for bite mark analysis like manual, radiographic, and computed assisted techniques. According to the studies of Van der Velden et al.,^[8] and Osman et al.,^[9] indirect methods for bite mark analysis using computed-assisted techniques were more accurate.

The American Board of Forensic Odontology (ABFO) guidelines state that the evidence should be gathered from both the victim and the suspect and a proper basis for evidence collection should be instituted. Any variations from these recommendations and guidelines should be questioned.^[10]

Dental Profiling

Dental Profiling is a specialized technique within the field of forensic odontology that involves the analysis & interpretation of dental characteristics to establish individual identities. It plays a crucial role in victim identification, criminal investigations & medicolegal cases. Here's a detailed overview of dental profiling;

Dental Characteristics : - Teeth are highly resistant to decomposition & can withstand extreme environmental conditions, making them valuable sources of identification evidence. Dental characteristics, such as - tooth morphology, restorations, anomalies, & pathologies are unique to each individual & can be used for identification purposes.

Dental Records Comparison : - Dental profiling often involves comparing ante-mortem (before death) dental records with post-mortem (after death) findings. Ante-mortem records may include dental charts, radiographs, treatment notes, & photographs provided by dentists or, obtained from dental clinics. Post-mortem records are collected during the forensic dental examination of the deceased individual. The comparison of ante-mortem & post-mortem records helps establish a positive identification or, exclude potential matches.

Radiographic Analysis : - Dental radiographs, such as bite-wing, periapical, & panoramic radiographs provide detailed information about tooth morphology, restorations & bony structures. Comparison of ante-mortem & post-mortem radiographs is a reliable method for identification, as radiographic features are unique & remain stable over time. Advanced imaging techniques, such as Cone beam computed tomography (CBCT), offer 3D visualization & enhance the accuracy of radiographic analysis.

Dental Restorations & Anomalies : - Dental restorations including fillings, crowns, bridges & implants can provide valuable identification evidence. The type, location, & material of restorations are recorded in dental charts & can be compared with post-mortem findings. Dental anomalies, such as missing teeth, supernumerary teeth, rotated or, tilted teeth & developmental defects can also aid in identification.

Dental Age Estimation : - Dental profiling techniques can estimate the age of an individual based on the development & eruption of teeth, as well as age related changes in dental

structures. Dental age estimation is particularly useful in cases involving unidentified juvenile remains or, in determining the legal age of an individual. Various methods, such as the Demirjian method, Radiographic method of Kvaal, Gustafson's methods are employed for dental age estimation.^[11]

Cheiloscopy

Cheiloscopy is a forensic procedure that uses human lip traces for identification.^[5] It is commonly used to compare the results of an autopsy and a patient's postmortem examinations.^[2] Unlike other methods, lip prints are unique and do not change during the lifetime of a person. They provide forensic investigators with sufficient information to perform their investigations.^[12]

The lip print pattern is determined by the mouth being open or closed. The lip has well defined grooves when the mouth is in a closed position, whereas the grooves in the open mouth posture are ill defined and difficult to understand. Changes in lip prints can also be caused by missing anterior teeth leading to support loss in that area. Lip print recording can be hampered by debris or moisture on the surface of the lip, a dense lipstick layer, or over stretching of cellophane tape.^[13]

Rugoscopy

In mammals, the presence, number, and arrangement of palatal rugae vary by species.^[14] They are asymmetrical in humans, which is a unique trait of humans.^[15,16] Palatal rugae can be utilized as a complement in edentulous mouths where postmortem identification of dental status is not possible. Many academics are concerned about the prospect of palatal rugae pattern alterations with aging and other external stimuli. Orthodontic tooth movement, neighboring tooth extractions, surgery of cleft palate, periodontal surgical procedures, and forced eruption of impacted canines are a few of the issues that need to be addressed.^[17]

Tongue Prints

Tongue prints are as unique as finger print.^[18] Even identical twins cannot have same tongue print. The color, shape, and surface of tongue are characteristic of each and every individual and emerging as a potential biometric tool in the field of forensic dentistry^[19]. The tongue biometric template is feasible with three views such as right lateral view, left lateral view, and profile view. The efficient template for shape of the tongue can be obtained by extraction of tongue algorithm of collecting points. The normalized histogram with Scale Invariant Feature Transform is utilized for texture analysis. By combining both the extraction techniques templates, the matching can be done.^[20] These databases can be collected and stored by dentist during routine dental procedure which can serve as forensic tool in future.

Determination of Sex

Sex determination is a crucial subset of forensic odontology that aids in an unknown person's identification following natural calamities, as well as chemical and nuclear bombing situations. There are four ways to do it.^[21]

1. Dimension and morphology of the craniofacial complex: The

mastoid, supraorbital ridge, skull size and architecture, zygomatic extensions, nasal aperture, and mandible gonial angle, as well as the pattern established by these traits, are all taken into consideration.

2. Sex difference in dimension of tooth: The most reliable approach for sex determination is to measure the mesiodistal and buccolingual dimensions. In males, both dimensions are larger than in females.
3. Tooth morphology: The male canine has a more prominent distal accessory ridge than the female. In females, the mandibular first molar has fewer cusps. These characteristics may be due to an evolutionary reduction in the size of the female lower jaw.
4. DNA analysis for sex determination: According to Das and his colleagues' investigation, sex determination might be acquired up to four weeks after death by examining the X and Y-chromosomes.

Facial Reconstruction

Forensic facial reconstruction is a quick, non invasive, and effective approach for identifying people from skeletal remains. This forensic tool combines scientific approaches with artistic abilities.^[22] There are two sorts of reconstruction techniques: two-dimensional (2D) and three dimensional (3D).^[23]

In the case of 2D face reconstruction, the method focuses to re-create the face from the skull using estimates of soft tissue depth based on the antemortem photographs.^[24] In the case of 3D manual reconstruction, a recreation of the face is performed by using clay, plastic, or wax directly on the skull of the victim which is to be identified. This method employs tissue depth markers of particular lengths to specify various depths of soft tissue.^[25]

DNA Analysis

It is a novel tool employed in forensic investigations due to its ability to overcome the effects of traumatism, heat, and autolytic processes. In addition, it allows investigators to perform DNA typing with minimal resources.^[26] DNA is found in various parts of the teeth, such as the pulp tissue, the cement, and the alveolar bone. In forensic cases, DNA can be extracted using a variety of methods.^[27] Genomic DNA and mitochondrial (mt) DNA are used in forensic investigations.

Digital Research

Accurate and comprehensive dental records are crucial in forensic odontology, particularly in identifying individuals. These records should include the patient's medical history, clinical examination, dental records, therapy, and follow-up information. Any errors in charting can invalidate the record. Dental records may also contain radiographs, study casts, impressions, and clinical pictures. In many European countries, registering dental data is mandatory, and erasing a patient's record requires state legislation permission. Digital imaging technologies, like Dental Cross, can also positively identify individuals. Teeth are often identified using two techniques: comparing previous dental records with PM dental characteristics or creating

a PM dental profile to guide the search for AM materials. Dental identification is critical, as teeth are more resistant to deterioration than other bodily tissues.^[28]

Saliva Analysis

Saliva analysis providing valuable information for identification and investigation purposes. Saliva contains DNA, enzymes, hormones, and other biomarkers that can be analyzed to identify individuals, detect diseases, and determine the presence of drugs or toxins. In forensic odontology, saliva analysis can be used to analyze saliva stains on bite marks, clothing, or other objects found at crime scenes. This can help investigators link suspects to crime scenes, identify victims, and reconstruct events. Additionally, saliva analysis can also be used to detect saliva on dental evidence, such as dentures or orthodontic appliances, aiding in the identification of human remains.^[28]

Amelogyphics

Amelogyphics is the study of enamel patterns. Since the enamel rod pattern varies by gender and is unique to each person, it can help with human identification. It also helps in age estimation, bite mark analysis, victim and suspect linkage. It is useful when DNA or fingerprints are unavailable. It can be applied to both living individuals and deceased bodies. Enamel rod patterns can be visualized using acid etching, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), or polarized light microscopy. It requires high magnification tools for clear pattern visualization.

After examining the enamel pattern of the left maxillary canine and first premolar in 30 male and 30 female volunteers using the cellulose acetate peel technique, Manjunath et al. came to the conclusion that the branched wavy sub pattern was the most prevalent kind by visual inspection.^[29]

AI Current Trend

AI and machine learning are now used to analyse rugae patterns digitally, improving accuracy and reducing human error. High resolution 3D laser scanners and CBCT allow detailed visualization and comparison of palatal rugae. 3D printing of palatal rugae models helps forensic experts reconstruct oral structures from remains. AI assisted rugae pattern classification are also recently evolved.

Recently use of 3D scanning technology allows for more detailed lip print analysis, especially in cases where prints are distorted on different surfaces. AI and machine learning algorithms are being used to enhance the classification and comparison of lip prints, reducing human error and improving accuracy. Next generation sequencing (NGS) has made it possible to analyze damaged and mixed DNA material with previously unheard of precision. By revealing information about tissue origin and environmental exposure, methods like forensic epigenetics and microbiome analysis have given DNA based evidence additional dimensions. Algorithms assess pulp to tooth ratio and tooth mineralization for accurate age prediction. The enamel of teeth contains sex specific proteins, such as AMELY and AMELX peptides, which remain intact even in ancient or

degraded remains. Studies suggest that differences in protein expression in dentin and cementum can help in sex identification.^[29]

Conclusion

Forensic odontology is a looming branch that holds a promising scope in forensic discipline. How much ever less the available remnant is, the forensic dentistry will try to resolve it. Forensic dentistry is constantly trying to update the available forensic tool and simultaneously developing novel tools for identification. Sometimes it plays adjunct role in identification procedure whereas sometimes plays main role in identification procedure. With the constantly developing novel tools and with the further research in the field of forensic odontology it is evident that soon this discipline will cherish an unconquerable position in the world of forensic science. Dentists should update their knowledge in this field since their contribution is undeniable for making the base of this discipline even stronger.^[18]

Future Proposal

Dental records are majorly contributing in solving forensic mysteries including personal identification. Unique IDs such as Aadhar cards are already linked with individuals bank accounts, driving license, PAN cards, registration certificates of the vehicles. We recommend that dental records such as Orthopantomogram (OPG) providing a holistic information about the individual dentition should be linked to individuals Aadhar cards.

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